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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Konvergent tahririyat mas'uliyati: Yangi O'zbekistonni barpo etish jarayonini yoritish tendensiyalari	16
Doniyorov Salim Musurmonovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy bilimlarini shakllantirish.....	23
Nazarov Odil Omanqulovich	
"Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasi"da ijtimoiy-pedagogik hamkorlikning o'rni	27
Abirova Umida Nazarovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda uchraydigan nutq nuqsonlarini oldini olish va uning ahamiyati.....	30
Akramov Dostonbek Ikromjon o'g'li	
Pedagogik jarayonda axloqiy qarashlarni shakllantirish usul va vositalari	34
Xudoykulova Shaxlo Mamaniyozovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarining ijodkorligini rivojlantirishda ta'limiy o'yinlarning ahamiyati	38
Salimova Dilmira Farxodovna	
Aholining iqtisodiy axborot savodxonligini oshirishdagi muammo va kamchiliklar	41
Rajabov Asliddin Xolmirzayevich	
Favqulodda vaziyatlar yo'nalishi ta'limida muloqotning ahamiyati.....	44
Boltayev Baxtiyor Yunusovich	
Biologiya ta'limi va raqamli texnologiyalar	48
E. Po'latova	
Boshlang'ich ta'limga tayyorlov guruhi bolalarini kasbga yo'naltirishda stem yondashuvining ahamiyati ...	51
Egamova Ravshanoy Surobjonovna	
O'zbekiston TIMSS natijalarini qanday yaxshilashi mumkin? Innovatsion ta'lim yondashuvlari va samarali strategiyalar.....	55
G'ayniddinov Shayxislom Tolibjon o'g'li	
Nutq kamchiliklarini bartaraf etishda mutaxassislar hamkorligi	60
Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi	
Developing Student's Critical Skills Through Technology-Enhanced English Lessons	63
Mavlonova Dildora Shuxrat qizi	
Bahrom Ro'zimuhammad she'rlarini o'qitishda integratsiya usulidan foydalanish	67
Nomozova Dilobar Suyun qizi	
Aksiologik yondashuvlar asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarda altruizm ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish: bosqichlar va tamoyillar	72
Norboyeva Moxigul Shavkat qizi	
3D Modeling of Virtual Chemical Laboratories	75
Qayumov Jamshid Ma'rufjon o'g'li	
Fostering Metacognitive Skills in Efl Learners Through Ai-Supported Instruction: a Review of Recent Literature	80
Ruzieva Maftuna	
Onlayn va gibrid ta'lim sharoitida mashinasozlik texnologiyasi faniga qiziqishni oshirishning nazariy asoslari.....	85
Sarimsakova Soxibaxon Raxmonjanovna	
Loyihalashtirilgan integral darslar samaradorligi (9-sinflar uchun "Metallar va ularning umumiy xususiyatlari" mavzusida).....	88
Sharipova Hakima Shavkatovna	
Metacognition and Self-Regulated Learning	92
Turayeva Nazira Ibragimovna	
Методические возможности совершенствования обучения научной письменной речи на основе коммуникативно-деятельностного подхода	95
Меденцева Наталья Петровна	
Transformatsion jarayonlarda tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish strategiyalari	100
Jonibekov Jasur Jonibekovich	

O'zbek milliy musiqasi: boy madaniyat va san'atning ajralmas qismi.....	105
Rustamova Maxsuma Farxodbek qizi	
Sharq va G'arbda tibbiyot fanlarining yaratilishi tarixi.....	108
Bakayev Najmiddin	
Didaktik o'yinlar bola faoliyatining asosiy vositasi sifatida.....	112
Egamova Madina Qobil qizi	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining konvergent-kreativ tafakkurini takomillashtirishning didaktik asoslari.....	116
Egamova Shukriya Amanovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida universal ta'lim faoliyatlari orqali tarbiyaviy maqsadlarga erishish imkoniyatlari	119
G'aybullayeva Nafisaxon Nosirjon qizi	
Matematika o'qitishning klassik metodlaridan zamonaviy usullariga o'tish	124
G'ofurov Jamoliddin Xusniddinovich	
Jahon miqyosida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	128
Hoshimova Dilnoza Boymirzoyevna, Mahmudova Zulfiya Homidovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning prognostik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish tamoyillari.....	131
Ikromova Munisa Sheraliyevna	
Bo'lajak muhandislarni kasbiy tayyorgarligini grafik ma'lumotlar asosida oshirishning didaktik asoslari	134
Jumanazarova Zuhra Qosimjonovna	
Sport va jismoniy tarbiya pedagogikasida innovatsion metodlar	138
Jumanova Iroda Shokirjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	141
Jumayeva Sarvinoz Ilhombekovna	
Talabalarda nutqiy tarkibiy tuzilmalarni shakllantirish texnologiyasi	145
Kiyamova Maxbuba Sultanovna	
Innovatsion yondoshuv asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning amaliy jihatlari	148
Mamadiyrov Jamol	
Ingliz tili matnlarini o'rganishda 6-sinf o'quvchilarining grammatik kompetensiyasini oshirish va tatbiq qilishning samarali usullari.....	152
Sharipova Firuza Mehriddinovna	
Kar va zaif eshituvchi yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining axborot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish modeli	155
Tursunov Hojiakbar Hamidullo o'g'li	
Maktabgacha ta'limda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim – pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	159
Xallokova Maksudaxon Ergashevna	
Altruistik xulq-atvorning shaxsiy va ijtimoiy determinantlari.....	162
Xatamova Ferangiz Ibodulloevna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy-pedagogik mahoratini teatr pedagogikasi vositalari orqali rivojlantirishning xorijiy va milliy tajribasi	166
Xudoyberganova Matluba Qulsoxatovna	
Refleksiv yondashuvning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va afzalliklari.....	170
Yodgorova Gulrux Farhodovna	
Совершенство методики формирования компетентности будущих студентов-искусствоведов в условиях цифрового образования.....	174
Юлдашев Эргаш Сабинович	
O'z-o'zini rivojlantirish tushunchasi va uning pedagogik mohiyati.....	177
Kudenov Temurbek Maxsetbaevich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish darslarida hikoya janrini o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish dolzarb muammo sifatida	180
Ergasheva Shoxida Nurmuxammadovna	
Ingliz tili darslarini interaktiv tashkil etishda raqamli ta'lim vositalarining o'rni va metodik yondashuvlar	185
Raxmatullayeva Barno Baxtiyor qizi	
The Effectiveness of Using Podcasts to Enhance Listening Comprehension and Vocabulary Acquisition in Secondary School English Classes.....	189
Meliboyev Zuxriddin Isroil ugli	

O'zbekiston tarixi darslarida pedagogik improvizatsiyani texnologiyalashtirish va raqamlashtirish imkoniyatlari	192
Ergasheva Muhayyoxon G'anijonovna	
Tasviriy faoliyat vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning badiiy-ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirishning samaradorligi.....	196
Arslanova Umidaxon Komiljon qizi	
Baxtli pedagoglar sirlari yoki kasbdagi subyektiv farovonlik	201
Adilova Zulfiya Djavdatovna	
Ayollarning siyosiy faolligini oshirishda gender kvotalarining o'rni	204
Abdukaxorova O'g'iloy Isroiljon qizi	
The Content of Developing Students' Communicative Culture Through a Bilingual Approach	207
Abdukhaliyeva Feruzakhon Ulugbek kizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi nutqida kamchiligi bo'lgan bolalar so'zlashuv nutqini shakllantirishda o'yin texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ahamiyati.....	210
Abdullayeva Ugiloy Djurayevna	
Chet tili intellektual va kasbiy rivojlanish kaliti	214
Aripova Sayida Abdalaxatovna	
Raqamli etiket: zamonaviy ta'limda yangi madaniyat talabi	217
Rasuljon Atamuratov	
Raqamli xiyonat: zamonaviy munosabatlar va sodiqlik inqirozi.....	221
Azizova Shodiya Utkur qizi	
Badiiy tarjimada leksik birliklarning lingvomadaniy aspektlari	224
Mardiyeva Maxbuba Shavkatovna	
O'quvchilarda funksional savodxonlikni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan dasturiy platformani pedagogik loyihalash.....	228
Obloqulov Sulaymon Maxmayusuf o'g'li	
Kurashchilar orasida jarohatlarning oldini olish: reabilitatsiya va profilaktik uslublar	232
Ochilova Sarvinoz Salim qizi	
Xalq og'zaki ijodi vositasida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini o'quvchilarning o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishga tayyorlashning pedagogik-psixologik jihatlari	236
Oxunova Nozimaxon Mirzag'ulom qizi	
Loyiha asosidagi o'qitish orqali yoshlarda liderlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirish usullari.....	239
Risvayeva Charos Zaydilla qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ingliz tilini o'yinlar vositasida o'rgatishga qaratilgan mashq va topshiriqlarning samaradorligi.....	242
Toshniyozova Dildora, Meliyeva Nargizaxon	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tarixiy va ma'naviy ideallarga aksiologik munosabatini rivojlantirish modeli	245
Tursunova Dilnoza Adhamjon qizi	
Shaxs rivojlanishida pedagogika va psixologiyaning o'rni	248
Umirova Guldona Jamoliddin qizi	
Toshkent shahri havosi ifloslanishining sabablari va oldini olish choralari	251
Ungalov Akmal Navruzovich	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida tuzilgan interaktiv platformalar va ulardan foydalanuvchi tajribasi	254
Xabirova Zulfiya Anvarbekovna	
Talabalar ijtimoiy faollik indeksini rivojlantirishda tyutorlik faoliyatining o'rni va ahamiyati	257
Xamrakuov Jasurbek Muxammadjon o'g'li	
Hozirgi davr pedagogikasida sharqona ta'limning ahamiyati.....	260
Yuldasheva Mastura Islamovna	
Пословицы и поговорки как отражение картины мира	263
Алламбергенова Шахноза Садатдиновна	

THE CONTENT OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE THROUGH A BILINGUAL APPROACH

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Abstract: This article examines the theoretical and practical foundations of developing students' communicative culture through a bilingual approach. It evaluates the role of bilingualism in education, highlights its importance in shaping intercultural communication skills, and presents effective methods for improving students' communicative competence using both native and foreign languages.

Key words: bilingual approach, communicative culture, intercultural communication, interactive learning, bilingual education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada talabalarning kommunikativ madaniyatini ikki tillilik yondashuvi orqali shakllantirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Unda ta'limdagi ikki tillilikning o'rni, uning madaniyatlararo muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati yoritiladi hamda ona tili va xorijiy til asosida talabalar kommunikativ kompetensiyasini oshirishga xizmat qiluvchi samarali usullar taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ikki tillilik yondashuvi, kommunikativ madaniyat, madaniyatlararo muloqot, interaktiv o'qitish, ikki tili ta'lim.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические основы формирования коммуникативной культуры студентов через билингвальный подход. Оценивается роль билингвизма в образовании, подчеркивается его значение в развитии навыков межкультурной коммуникации, а также предлагаются эффективные методы повышения коммуникативной компетентности студентов с использованием родного и иностранного языков.

Ключевые слова: билингвальный подход, коммуникативная культура, межкультурная коммуникация, интерактивное обучение, билингвальное образование.

INTRODUCTION

In today's era of globalization and rapid technological advancement, education must prioritize the development of communicative skills among learners. For students studying foreign languages in particular, the ability to express ideas clearly, engage in conversations, and participate in intercultural dialogue is essential. Within this framework, the bilingual approach is gaining prominence as a contemporary method in modern educational systems.

Bilingual education not only strengthens language proficiency but also fosters personal development, cultural awareness, and social adaptability. This article examines the content, methodology, and pedagogical potential of enhancing communicative competence through a bilingual approach.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design to explore how a bilingual approach contributes to the development of students' communicative culture. Data were collected through classroom observations, semi-structured interviews with language teachers, and analysis of students' oral and written language tasks. A purposive sampling method was used to select participants from bilingual educational settings at the secondary school level. Thematic analysis was applied to identify key patterns related to language use, intercultural competence, and communicative behavior. The study focused on both cognitive and sociolinguistic dimensions of bilingual communication, ensuring a holistic understanding of how bilingual instruction enhances communicative culture.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The bilingual approach involves the simultaneous or alternate use of two languages—typically the native and a foreign language—in the learning process. It is implemented through several educational models.

Picture 1: Educational models

CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) is an educational approach where students learn a subject (such as science, history, or math) through a foreign language. In this model, the language is not only the goal but also the medium of instruction. CLIL has a dual focus: students learn subject content (e.g., biology, geography) and language (e.g., English) at the same time. Language is used as a tool, not merely a subject. This approach encourages real-world communication and critical thinking. For example, instead of teaching “Temperaments” in Uzbek and “English vocabulary” separately, a CLIL lesson would teach temperaments in English, allowing students to learn psychology while improving their English skills simultaneously.

Code-switching is the practice of alternating between two or more languages or language varieties within a single conversation, sentence, or phrase. It is a natural behavior among bilinguals and multilinguals, occurring both intentionally and unconsciously. A simple example would be: “I really liked the presentation, lekin u biroz uzun bo’ldi.” (Translation: “I really liked the presentation, but it was a bit long.”) Code-switching is used for several reasons: to express something more clearly in another language, when a specific concept does not exist in one language, to express identity or cultural connection, or for emotional emphasis. In educational contexts, teachers may use code-switching to scaffold understanding, especially when students struggle to grasp complex concepts in English. This method helps learners comprehend challenging ideas, enables smoother classroom communication, gradually immerses them into the target language, and builds confidence before fluency is achieved.

Interactive bilingual tasks are communication-based activities that actively involve students in using both their native and foreign languages. These include role-plays, debates, interviews, discussions, and presentations. Such tasks aim to develop both linguistic proficiency and communicative competence, foster critical thinking and collaboration, and promote intercultural awareness through authentic, socially meaningful language use. Scholars like Bialystok (2011) and Cummins (2000) emphasize the cognitive advantages of bilingualism, such as enhanced memory, attention, and problem-solving skills. Communicative culture refers to a person’s ability to engage in meaningful, respectful, and effective communication in various social and cultural contexts. It goes beyond mere language skills and includes understanding the ethical, social, and linguistic norms that govern interactions in diverse settings. The core components of communicative culture include linguistic competence, which involves accurate use of grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and stylistic choices to ensure clarity and coherence. Sociocultural competence is also vital—it encompasses understanding and respecting cultural differences in communication, including formal and informal registers, cultural gestures, and audience expectations. Speech etiquette—politeness, patience, appropriate turn-taking, and active listening—further maintains respectful and inclusive interaction. Non-verbal cues like tone, eye contact, and gestures are equally important. Interactive competence, the final component, is the ability to initiate, maintain, and conclude conversations effectively through asking questions, expressing opinions, and contributing meaningfully to group discussions. Together, these competencies shape a person’s ability to express themselves, build relationships, and navigate multilingual environments successfully. Improving communicative culture in bilingual classrooms requires a strategic combination of interactive, context-rich methods. One effective strategy is designing bilingual lesson plans based on texts in both Uzbek and English, encouraging comparative linguistic analysis and cross-lin-

guistic understanding. Simulated scenarios such as job interviews, travel dialogues, or healthcare conversations allow learners to engage in authentic, purposeful bilingual interactions, enhancing fluency and confidence. Thematic debates, where students argue their viewpoints in both languages, foster critical thinking and adaptability across formal and informal language use. Writing tasks—bilingual essays, journals, and analytical papers—build metalinguistic awareness and strengthen written communication across languages. Incorporating bilingual media—podcasts, videos, and articles—exposes students to real-world language, diverse accents, and cultural subtleties. These strategies not only reinforce language acquisition but also cultivate a confident, culturally sensitive, and respectful communicative identity. Practical outcomes show that students trained through bilingual approaches speak with greater clarity, coherence, and cultural appropriateness.

CONCLUSION

The bilingual approach serves as a dynamic and transformative educational strategy that extends far beyond the mere acquisition of linguistic competence. It plays a critical role in shaping students' overall communicative culture by fostering not only their ability to express themselves in multiple languages, but also their sensitivity to cultural nuances, diverse perspectives, and social norms. Through bilingual instruction, learners develop intercultural understanding, which is essential in today's interconnected world where cross-cultural interactions are frequent and often inevitable. Moreover, the bilingual approach nurtures tolerance, empathy, and a heightened sense of social responsibility, encouraging students to become respectful, open-minded, and socially conscious individuals.

This approach holds particular significance for 21st-century learners, who must be equipped with the competencies required for global citizenship, including effective participation in international dialogues, adaptability in multicultural environments, and collaboration across linguistic and cultural boundaries. In light of its broad educational benefits, further efforts are needed to enhance the bilingual model through the development of specialized lesson plans, digitally integrated learning resources, and innovative assessment tools. These elements should be tailored to meet the evolving needs of bilingual learners and aligned with contemporary pedagogical standards. Advancing these components not only supports more effective implementation of the bilingual approach but also opens new avenues for research, innovation, and long-term application in multilingual education settings.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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